

INTERLAMINAR TOUGHENING MECHANISMS: IN SITU GROWTH AND MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

Micromechanistic simulation of constrained interlaminar fracture occurring during delamination of toughened materials has received limited attention within the polymer composites community. With recent advances in computational resources and the development of arbitrary cracking models, such as the Augmented Finite Element Method (A-FEM), more complex microstructures can now be tackled featuring multiple interacting cracks. It has been established that Mode I crack propagation in particle-toughened interlayers within a CFRP laminate involve a process zone rather than a distinct crack tip. This involves multiple cracks forming ahead of the main crack that then coalesce, leaving behind bridging ligaments that may then provide traction across the crack flanks. Preliminary idealised 2D AFEM models are presented in this work, that highlight the relative role of neat resin to ply interface cohesion, and the incidence of ‘idealised de-bonds’/discontinuities, in maintaining the crack path within the interlayer. Four-dimensional time-resolved computed tomography (CT) experiments complement the idealised models, with the chronology of damage events and resultant crack paths being directly identified in different toughened microstructures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) are increasingly used in primary aerospace structures, however, significant loss in mechanical properties can be caused by low velocity impact events that may occur in service [1]. The dispersion of secondary phase particles within interlaminar regions has been shown to be effective in reducing the spread of delaminations caused by impacts via toughening of the interlayer [2–4]. Micromechanical understanding and quantification of interlaminar failure processes in these complex particle-toughened interlayers is not well established, with corresponding uncertainty in precisely how added toughness arises. In bulk resins, toughening mechanisms such as; crack pinning [5], crack path deflection [5, 6], particle bridging [7], particle/resin de-bonding and subsequent void growth [8], and localised shear yielding [9] have been identified. However, it has been established that an improvement in bulk resin toughness will not translate directly into an equal improvement in interlaminar toughness, which has been attributed to the constraining action of the surrounding plies [4, 10]. Additionally, fibre interfaces also offer an alternate crack path that may result in propagation along or inside the ply, thus avoiding the toughened interlayer [11, 12]. Previous work has shown that particles can draw the crack path away from the fibre interface by de-bonding ahead of the ‘crack tip’, and that the crack path preferentially follows particle-rich regions ahead of the main crack, thus enabling a more tortuous ligament-rich crack path to develop [13]. Other authors have suggested that in similar micron-sized particle-toughened systems, smaller, uniformly distributed particles (~10 µm) will result in a higher interlaminar fracture toughness, but it is not yet completely clear why there appears to be an optimum micro-structure [14].

Through the use of synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT), *in situ* non-destructive identification of micro-mechanisms is possible within the bulk material while avoiding cross-sectioning artefacts associated with preparing conventional specimens for microscopy. In this work, time-resolved *in situ* tests have been conducted on four different material systems using a simple wedge loading to generate Mode I loading conditions. This allowed the influence of local microstructural irregularity on the location of damage initiation and crack path evolution to be observed in a chronological manner. Additionally, the effect of particle type and size on the fracture micro-mechanisms was explored, whilst maintaining all the other constituents between the material systems. A preliminary 2D model is presented in this work, where the Augmented-Finite Element Method (A-FEM) [15] has been used to simulate a particle-toughened interlayer with idealised particle de-bonds represented by ‘strong discontinuities’. The effects of the relative cohesive strengths of the neat resin and ply interface, and the neighbouring ply stiffness, on the crack path were explored parametrically. This was simulated by varying the fraction of discontinuities ahead of the crack tip and identifying when the crack will propagate to the ply interface.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Developmental CFRPs were prepared by Cytec Industries and manufactured and cured according to a standard aerospace autoclave cycle. A 16 ply uni-directional layup (~3 mm thick) was prepared from pre-preg with a 40 μm thick Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) insert placed at mid-plane. Proprietary intermediate modulus carbon fibres (~5.4 μm in diameter) were used as the primary reinforcement, and secondary-phase thermoplastic toughening particles were confined to ~30 μm thick interlayers. Four different particle systems are presented in this work, with the fibre type, sizing, base resin and particle volume fraction being consistent between the systems. The different material systems are described in Table 1. The particles in Materials B and D are made from the same proprietary thermoplastic, with Material A particles made from a different thermoplastic (again proprietary). Material C features two distinct particle types; one type that was seen to have no clear X-ray contrast, and another that was distinguishable via CT. Whilst the composition of the toughening phases is proprietary, relative (normalised) toughness effects are shown in Table 1.

System	Description	Particle V_f	Normalised $G_{IC-Pmax}$
Material A	5-10 μm spherical particles	13%	1.0
Material B	5-20 μm irregularly shaped particles	13%	0.80
Material C	Hybrid with 5-20 μm irregularly shaped and other particles*	13%	0.64
Material D	20-40 μm irregularly shaped particles	13%	0.58

Table 1: Material systems overview [* particles in this case show no appreciable X-ray contrast for conditions tested]

2.2 Fracture Toughness Testing

Standard 175 x 20 x 3 mm geometries with a 65 mm long PTFE insert were used for the Mode I fracture toughness tests, with five specimens tested for each material at a cross-head displacement rate of 2.5 mm/min. Aluminium blocks were attached to the specimens, which were subsequently pre-cracked in Mode I, and reloaded to propagate the crack for 50 mm in a double cantilever beam arrangement. A summary of the mean and standard deviation for the initiation fracture toughness calculated at peak load can be seen in Fig. 1. The initiation fracture toughness was calculated according to [16]:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2Ba} \quad (1)$$

where P is the load [N], δ is the cross-head displacement [m], B is the specimen width [m], and a is the crack length [m].

Figure 1: Mean and standard deviation for the Mode I initiation fracture toughness (G_{IC}) calculated at the peak load and corresponding displacement

2.2 Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography

SRCT was conducted at the Swiss Light Source (SLS) on the TOMCAT beamline at the Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland. Scans were conducted at a voxel resolution of 0.325 μm , with a detector size of 2560 x 2160 pixels. A beam energy of 15 kV was used, with 1501 projections taken at an exposure of 150 ms for the 180-degree rotation. A propagation distance of 23 mm was used in order to gain some phase enhanced contrast, a technique that can improve the contrast of the edges between two materials of similar attenuation (see [17]). The 3D datasets were reconstructed at the SLS using the in-house GRIDREC method [18].

2.3 Specimen Geometry and Loading

A specimen cross-section of 2.5 x 3 mm was used to provide a reasonably uniform X-ray path through all angles of rotation. The specimens were 150 mm long, with a 10 mm long PTFE insert placed at mid-plane to control the initiation of fracture. A wedge was driven into the mid-plane using a purpose built *in situ* rig shown in Fig. 2. The square ram ensured that no torsional loading was applied to the specimen during the experiment. An initial loading step grew the crack a distance of ~5 mm from the edge of the PTFE insert following which the specimen was scanned. The specimen was subsequently loaded to achieve about 200 μm of crack extension and scanned again: this process was then repeated three times allowing crack extension to be captured.

Figure 2: SRCT configuration for testing

3 COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING

3.1 Augmented Finite Element Method

2D augmented finite elements (A-FEs) developed by Liu *et al.* [15] have been used here. The elements have been shown to account for arbitrary intra-element cracks and their interactions without the need for extra nodes as in the Phantom Node Method, or additional ‘external’ Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) as in the Extended Finite Element Method [15]. The calculated crack displacements are the natural outcome of elemental equilibrium, rather than assuming deformation modes for elemental displacement enrichment. This is achieved by introducing internal node pairs with displacements as internal nodal DoFs that are later condensed at the element level. Following crack initiation, the forces on the crack faces during separation are calculated according to a user defined cohesive law. Significant for this work is that the augmentation procedure can be repeated on the same element, allowing for multiple intra-element cracks. This ability allows for bifurcating and coalescing cracks to be accounted for, which is critical in simulating the damage evolution observed in the materials presented in this work. Additionally, the elements can be integrated into standard Finite Element (FE) packages, such as ABAQUS™ via user subroutines, because the method uses standard finite element shape functions.

3.2 Preliminary Numerical Modelling

Fig. 3 illustrates the interlayer between the two plies with three embedded ‘strong discontinuities’/de-bonds (*i.e.* no traction across the faces) placed in the region of interest after an initial pre-crack. The dotted line along the bottom of the interlayer indicates the placement of a ‘weak’ discontinuity, such that the elements will only crack along the interface should the peak cohesive stress be exceeded. The model is pinned on the right hand side, and a displacement controlled loading is applied on the top and bottom plies on the left hand side. Two separate element definitions were given to the neat resin and the ply/interface elements, such that the effects of the relative toughness’s of the two competing mechanisms could be explored with respect to the crack path. The thickness of the interlayer is consistent with the $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$ seen in the CT data, and stiffness of the resin was taken to be 4 GPa, with the neighbouring ply stiffness of 300 GPa. Currently, there is limited information regarding suitable cohesive parameters to define resin and ply interface properties at such length-scales, therefore only the relative toughness between the two competing mechanisms are explored the present paper. This was implemented by changing the critical cohesive stress whilst maintaining the shape parameter and critical opening. In the first instance, the Mode I and Mode II cohesive strengths were assumed to be equal.

The output of the model determines how many discontinuities are followed as the proportion of de-bonds/‘strong discontinuities’ ahead of the tip is reduced. In doing so, the effects of the neighbouring ply stiffness (between 150 – 3000 GPa), and the relative toughness between the ply/interface and resin (between 0.6 – 0.8) on the crack path could be explored. Fig. 4(a) - (d) illustrate the four potential outcomes that are supported by the model, whereby the crack path can follow from zero to three discontinuities in the region of interest. Fig. 4(e) shows an example of the crack path reaching the region of interest, following which the ply/interface fails and draws the crack path towards it with complete separation shown in Fig. 4(f). Reducing the extent of the fraction of discontinuities is intended to simulate fewer potential particle de-bond locations as the particle volume fraction is decreased and/or a stronger particle interface strength.

Figure 3: Illustration of the interlayer models and the region of interest containing ‘strong discontinuities’/ de-bonds in each subset (not to scale)

Figure 4: Illustration of the potential model outputs (a-d) and example model results (e-f)

4 RESULTS

The damage evolution captured during the multiple load steps conducted in this work captured a total crack growth of about 1 mm. Figs. 4 and 6 illustrate a ~200 μm crack growth step that was chosen to illustrate typical details captured in these experiments. The crack growth direction is from left to right, with the post-growth slice placed below the corresponding pre-growth slice.

4.1 Mode I Damage Evolution

Fig. 5(a) shows the Mode I ‘crack tip’ in Mat. A; where the damage progression was identified to initiate from particles cracking from within, followed by crack coalescence, and the formation of particle-bridging ligaments. Particles only appear to de-bond partially closer to the developing ‘main crack’, indicating that the particle/resin interface is relatively strong. This suggests that the bridging mechanism (in this material) originates from the ability for the particles to deform plastically whilst remaining bonded to the crack flanks. However, the bridging ligaments in Mat. B are formed from the surrounding epoxy resin rather than the particles. This is seen in Fig. 5(b), suggesting that the particles in this system de-bond too readily to be effective at providing toughness enhancing traction forces. In the 3D volume, larger ligaments are seen to occur and are formed from a combination of particle and resin. However, predominantly small resin-only ligaments are featured in this material system. Fig. 5 also highlights the microstructural irregularity seen in these systems, with (i) stray fibres in the interlayer, (ii) particle depleted regions, and a range of particle shapes and sizes. Previous work has shown that the crack path preferentially follows particle de-bonds, and that large particle-depleted regions will result in the crack propagating towards the ply/interface [13].

Figure 5: Mode I damage evolution following a load step in (a) Mat. A and (b) Mat. B

Fig. 6(a) shows crack progression in Mat. C, where the microstructure appears strongly partitioned between the top and the bottom of the interlayer. The visible particles are dispersed over the top of the interlayer and have de-bonded as seen previously in Fig. 5(b). The particles along the bottom were not observed to de-bond, suggesting that the effective interface strength between these particles and the surrounding resin is stronger than the visible particles. The crack path follows these de-bonded particles, with the bridging ligaments formed from the bulk resin. On the left hand side of Fig. 6(a), there is clear indication of a failing ligament (indicated at (i)). The remaining ligament has visibly thinned, suggesting that the epoxy deforms plastically, consistent with previous authors' findings of plastic deformation [19]. Examining the whole volume, intralaminar failure is observed to occur in about 12% of the scanned volume, which was not observed for the other materials. This may imply that the lack of readily de-bonding particles ahead of the tip has caused the crack path to enter a more energetically favourable path. Fig. 6(b) shows the crack path in Mat. D. The variation of particle size in this microstructure is more evident, and qualitatively, it appears that larger particles de-bond more readily than the smaller ones. As with Mat. B and C, the bridging ligaments in this system are formed from the epoxy resin, where smaller resin strands are present along with thicker ligaments (seen at (ii)).

Figure 6: Mode I damage evolution following a load step in (a) Mat. C and (b) Mat. D

4.2 Crack Path Modelling

From the CT data, it may be inferred that the presence of de-bonds ahead of the main crack plays a role in keeping the crack away from the ply/interface, as particle-depleted regions have been seen to promote crack propagation along the ply interface. Fig. 7(a) shows the effects of varying the relative cohesive strength between the resin and the ply/interface on the crack path. The extent of de-bonding ahead of the crack tip was explored by varying the fraction of discontinuities in the subsets shown in Fig. 4. It was shown that as this fraction reduced (left to right), that the crack path was drawn towards the ply sooner. This may simulate the effect of particle-depleted regions and/or a toughened interlayer with a lower particle volume fraction. Fig. 7(b) shows that varying the ply stiffness from 150 GPa – 3000 GPa has no significant effect on the crack path. However, it is clear in Fig. 7(a) that the relative strength/toughness of the ply/interface is critical to the crack path, where a low ply/interface strength will provide the lower energy crack path and result in crack propagation along the interface sooner. Although this is an idealised representation of the real systems, the traction free discontinuities can be given properties allowing the simulation of the competition between the particle interface, ply interface and neat resin properties to be explored.

Figure 7: Illustration showing (a) significant effects of the relative resin to ply/interface toughness's and (b) no real effect being caused by the ply

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

To the best of the authors' knowledge, these time-series experiments are the first to capture Mode I crack growth in such toughened material systems at such high resolutions, thus clarifying micromechanistic issues, such as the chronology of potential processes such as particle deformation, cracking and/or de-bonding. The evolution of damage in Mat. A initiated from the particles cracking from within, with the bridging ligaments in the wake formed from the thermoplastic particles themselves. However, the Mat. B, C and D systems featured bridging ligaments formed from the surrounding epoxy resin, with particles de-bonding ahead of the main crack front. The performance of the smaller 5-20 μm sized particles in Mat B produced a 27 % higher G_{IC} than Mat. D, which contained the 20-40 μm sized particles of the same material. The preliminary model has shown that the competition between the resin and ply interface properties is important in determining the crack path, along with the extent of discontinuities ahead of the main crack front. It is thought that the optimum microstructure will feature just the right amount of de-bonds in order to keep the crack away from the ply interface. Future work will aim to give the current 'strong discontinuities' cohesive properties to simulate the particle bridging seen in Mat. A, and eventually build towards using particles with interfaces to build a more physically representative model.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. O. W. Richardson and M. J. Wisheart, Review of low-velocity impact properties of composite materials, *Compos. Part A*, **27**, 1996, pp. 1123–1131.
- [2] M. Yasaei, I. P. Bond, R. S. Trask, and E. S. Greenhalgh, Mode I interfacial toughening through discontinuous interleaves for damage suppression and control, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **43**, no. 1, 2012, pp. 198–207.
- [3] M. Yasaei, I. P. Bond, R. S. Trask, and E. S. Greenhalgh, Mode II interfacial toughening through discontinuous interleaves for damage suppression and control, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **43**, no. 1, 2012, pp. 121–128.
- [4] S. Singh and I. K. Partridge, Mixed-Mode Fracture in an Interleaved Carbon-Fibre/Epoxy Composite, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **55**, 1996, pp. 319–327.
- [5] S.-Y. Fu, X.-Q. Feng, B. Lauke, and Y.-W. Mai, Effects of particle size, particle/matrix interface adhesion and particle loading on mechanical properties of particulate-polymer composites, *Compos. Part B Eng.*, **39**, no. 6, 2008, pp. 933–961.
- [6] M. Zamanian, M. Mortezaei, B. Salehnia, and J. E. Jam, Fracture toughness of epoxy polymer modified with nanosilica particles: Particle size effect, *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, **97**, 2013, pp. 193–206.
- [7] A. G. Evans, Z. B. Ahmad, D. G. Gilbert, and P. W. R. Beaumont, Mechanisms of toughening in rubber toughened polymers, *Acta Met.*, **34**, no. 1, 1986, pp. 79–87.
- [8] Y. Huang and A. J. Kinloch, Modelling of the toughening mechanisms in rubber-modified epoxy polymers, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **27**, 1992, pp. 2763–2769.
- [9] Y. Huang and A. J. Kinloch, The sequence of initiation of the toughening micromechanisms in rubber-modified epoxy polymers, *Polymers (Basel)*, **33**, no. 24, 1992, pp. 5338–5340.

- [10] M. R. Groleau, Y. Shi, A. F. Yee, J. L. Bertram, H. J. Sueb, and P. C. Yang, Mode II Fracture of Composites Interlayered with Nylon Particles, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **56**, 1996, pp. 1223–1240.
- [11] N. Sela and O. Ishai, Interlaminar fracture toughness and toughening of laminated composite materials: a review, *Composites*, **20**, no. 5, 1989, pp. 423–435.
- [12] D. J. Bull, A. E. Scott, S. M. Spearing, and I. Sinclair, The influence of toughening-particles in CFRPs on low velocity impact damage resistance performance, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **58**, 2014, pp. 47–55.
- [13] G. Borstnar, M. N. Mavrogordato, L. Helfen, I. Sinclair, and S. M. Spearing, Interlaminar fracture micro-mechanisms in toughened carbon fibre reinforced plastics investigated via synchrotron radiation computed tomography and laminography, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **71**, 2015, pp. 176–183.
- [14] H.-M. Hsiao, C.-N. Ni, M.-D. Wu, and C.-W. Lin, A novel optical technique for observation of global particle distribution in toughened composites, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **43**, no. 9, 2012, pp. 1523–1529.
- [15] W. Liu, Q.D. Yang, S. Mohammadizadeh, and X.Y. Su, An efficient augmented finite element method for arbitrary cracking and crack interaction in solids, *Int. J. Num. Meth. Eng.*, **99**, 2014, pp. 438-468.
- [16] S. Hashemi, A. J. Kinloch, and J. G. Williams, Mechanics and Mechanisms of Delamination in a Poly (ether sulphone) - Fibre Composite, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **37**, 1990, pp. 429–462.
- [17] P. Cloetens, M. Pateyron-Salomé, J. Y. Buffière, G. Peix, J. Baruchel, F. Peyrin, and M. Schlenker, Observation of microstructure and damage in materials by phase sensitive radiography and tomography, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **81**, no. 9, 1997, p. 5878.
- [18] F. Marone and M. Stampanoni, GRIDREC software, *J. Synchrotron Rad.*, **19**, 2012, pp. 1029–1037.
- [19] R. Bagheri, B. T. Marouf, and R. A. Pearson, Rubber-Toughened Epoxies: A Critical Review, *Polym. Rev.*, **49**, no. 3, 2009, pp. 201–225.